

Human-Inspired Haptic-Based Planning and Control for Robotic Sliding Movements

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Abstract—This work presents a human-inspired haptic-based framework for planning and controlling a robotic manipulator during sliding movements over ridged surfaces. We use the DIGIT soft optical tactile sensor to detect surface textures, and deep learning techniques to approximate tactile flow by evaluating optical flow (OF) from collected images. A dataset is created to train a neural network (RAFT) to compute dense OF fields, representing the tactile perception component. The robot motion control mimics human unbiased musculoskeletal proprioception, using Model Predictive Control (MPC) and a Kalman Filter to adjust trajectory based on tactile feedback. Experimental results show promising performance in real-time control. The framework demonstrates potential for future applications in robotic manipulation and tactile feedback systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of tactile feedback into the sensory-motor system has emerged as a promising approach to enhance movement control and assess sensory-motor disorders [1]. In [2] a method for controlling hand movements using tactile illusions was presented, proposing MPC framework that adjusts hand motions to guide participants to a given target while sliding their fingerpad over a ridged disk toward a different one. The idea is to implement haptic retargeting in mixed-reality applications. In particular, the authors relied on the findings from [3], according to which, when blindfolded individuals slide their finger forward along a surface with ridges, the perceived motion direction is a weighted sum (the weights are based on the reliability of the sensory channel) of muscular-skeletal proprioception, which is unbiased, and tactile motion estimate, which is biased toward the direction perpendicular to the ridges as accounted by the tactile flow model. Consequently, participants adjusted the movement in the opposite direction of the perceived tactile motion.

In this work, we develop a human-inspired haptic-based framework for planning and controlling a robot manipulator, focusing on sliding movements over a plate with ridges. This system requires the ability to perceive the ridges' direction, similarly to human ability. Soft optical tactile sensors emerged as effective devices for replicating and integrating human tactile abilities into artificial systems, among the existing models, we choose the DIGIT sensor [4], which detects various tactile stimuli through surface shading caused by internal light sources. We employed the DIGIT to detect the ridges and evaluate the optical flow from the collected images using deep-learning techniques. The OF is the visual counterpart of tactile flow and the bias perception toward a direction perpendicular to a ridge holds in both perceptual domain, the so-called Barber Pole Illusion. We hence used OF to retrieve tactile motion estimates.

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Fig. 1: Problem overview

We created a suitable dataset constituted of pairs of two subsequent frames collected during sliding movements over a plate with ridges, and we evaluated its associated OF, as Ground-Truth, with EpicFlow [5], a technique for OF estimation. Then, we trained the RAFT [6], a recurrent neural network architecture to compute dense OF fields between image pairs. The estimated OF constitutes the tactile component of our framework, while the robot motion control stands for proprioception. Then, as done in [2] with human participants, we regulate the robot trajectory by directing the end-effector to an arbitrary point A (the corresponding angle w.r.t. the vertical midline of the plate is P_R), different from the preset reaching-point B (the corresponding angle w.r.t. the vertical midline of the plate is θ_V), by dynamically re-orienting the ridged plate using an MPC strategy that controls the DC motor that suitable rotate the plate to have the optimal ridge direction. The goal was to create a system to mimic human behavior as a testbed to perform neuroscientific and clinical investigations.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The goal is to integrate tactile feedback into the sensory-motor system to direct the robot's end effector in real-time, leveraging the model predictive control introduced in [2]. Developing the entire framework for a robotic manipulator involves two steps. First, artificially replicate the human sense of touch by approximate the tactile flow [3] with OF obtained from ridge images collected with the DIGIT. To this aim, we recorded images of DIGIT during sliding movements over a plate with ridges for creating the dataset used to train the neural network for OF estimation. Second, adapt the framework presented in [2] to account for kinematic information rather than musculoskeletal proprioception.

A. Artificial Tactile Perception

For data collection, we made multiple sliding of the DIGIT sensor on different plates with different ridge orientations to record videos from which extracting couples of frames (fig. 2a). In total we extracted an amount of 800 samples (couples), which we split in training+validation (80%), and in testing (20%). The liberalization process required evaluating

Fig. 2: (a) shows the DIGIT and the plate with ridges, (b) shows an image sample on the left, and the RAFT output with the OF vector on the right (actual vector in white, estimated in black).

ground-truth optical flow corresponding to each frame pair. For this evaluation we exploited both Horn and Schunck theory [7] as a model-based approach, and EpicFlow [5] as a model-free method. We obtained the best results by using EpicFlow since it is a more refined approach that, different from the Horn-Schunck technique which can struggle in areas with discontinuities or large motion, enhances flow estimation by combining the advantages of sparse matching with edge-preserving interpolation. Then, we evaluate the difference between the actual vector perpendicular to the ridge and the estimated one, in terms of the angle between the ridge line and optical flow vector, and used it as parameter to evaluate the effectiveness of the network. Indeed it is the angle information that we will use in our Human-Inspired Haptic-Based control strategy. The validation results are promising since we got an average error of about 13° over all samples (fig. 2b).

B. Model Predictive Control Strategy

To exploit the role of both tactile and kinematic (extracutaneous) information in hand motion control, we involved the strategy based on Model Predictive Control (MPC) proposed in [2]. We first implemented a Kalman Filter (KF) to estimate the perceived angular orientation of the hand by integrating tactile feedback information with the robot's kinematics (musculoskeletal proprioception in [2]: $\theta_k = \omega_T T_k + \omega_P P_k$. Here T_k and P_k are the tactile feedback and proprioception, respectively, while ω_T and ω_P are the weights of the two contributions. Then, at each time, the output θ_k is used to find the optimal ridge orientation. The optimization is achieved through the MPC by evaluating a cost function that minimizes the error between the estimated perceived hand direction and the virtual target, and the error between the simulated hand motion and the real target: $J(k) = (\hat{\theta}_k - \theta_V)^2 + (P_k - P_R)^2$. It is worth noting that θ_k depends on the ridge orientation T_k as it directly affects the tactile feedback. Having the optimal ridge configuration to guide the robot end-effector through the desired point, the new desired angular orientation of the robot direction is estimated with the KF and used as information to define the position control law of the manipulator: $u_k = -K(\hat{\theta}_k - P_R)$.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The experimental setup involved a manipulator robot (Franka Emika Panda) and a plate with ridges, actuated by a DC motor that provides rotary motion. The goal is to guide the robot end-effector toward a desired point, leveraging the tactile illusions generated by the ridges. The project is organized using the ROS framework, with two PCs that communicate through a UDP connection: one handles DIGIT sensor data extraction for neural network inference, the other manages robot control, planning, and execution of MPC and KF. Preliminary results were obtained by commanding the robot toward a point B (green point in fig. 3) (10° w.r.t. to the vertical midline of the plate) and controlling it with the

Fig. 3: End-effector trajectory. ThetaV, i.e., θ_V , is the preset direction, and PR, i.e., P_R , is the actual desired direction.

proposed haptic-based human-like strategy toward point A (red point in fig. 3) (-10° w.r.t. to the vertical midline of the plate). Fig. 3 shows that the proposed system is able to correctly redefine the robot trajectory during sliding motions, bringing the end-effector to the desired final point.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In conclusion, this work presents a novel approach that integrates a soft optical tactile sensor and a model-free strategy for evaluating OF. This is used as the approximation of tactile flow to retrieve tactile information during the contact between the sensor and a plate with ridges, as demonstrated in [8]. Since it was demonstrated that the perceived hand movement results from a combination of traditional proprioceptive cues and tactile feedback, we integrate the obtained information into a robot framework to guide the robot motion toward a given target, while the original kinematic planning was directed toward another target position over a ridged surface. This was done to simulate human behavior and haptic retargeting implementation in mixed reality. We implemented a KF for estimating end-effector direction by comparing tactile and kinematic cues, and MPC strategy to evaluate the optimal orientation of the plate with ridges that guide the robot through the desired point. Preliminary results are promising with the potential to create a controlled testbed for testing neuroscientific hypotheses. Additionally, it has the potential to assist individuals with visual impairments or simulate protected environments for studying and understanding human behavior.

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